

Regional Assessment of the Seagrass *Halodule ciliata* (Hartog) Hartog in the Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion (Bioregion 2) for the IUCN Red List ^{1,2}

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PLANTAE - TRACHEOPHYTA - LILIOPSIDA - ALISMATALES - CYMODOCEACEAE - *Halodule* - *ciliata*

Common Names: Species code: Hi (English)

Synonyms: No Synonyms

Taxonomic Note: *Halodule ciliata* was originally described as *Diplanthera ciliata*. Current taxonomic status is unclear, as for most other *Halodule* species, until studies which combine examination of type material, descriptions of leaf tip morphology and genetic analyses are carried out. Analysis of the type specimen at the US Natural History Herbarium shows a distinctly different leaf and leaf tip morphology compared to any of the other *Halodule* species (den Hartog 1970, F. Short personal communication). However, Woodson et al (1975) elected to include *Halodule ciliata* under *Halodule wrightii* in their Flora of Panama.

Red List Status
CR Critically Endangered (IUCN version 14) B1, B2a, C2a (i, ii), D Possibly Extinct
Extent of occurrence (EOO) = 4km ² ; Area of occupancy (AOO) = 4km ²

Red List Assessment

Assessment Information

Assessor(s): Creed, J.C., Samper-Villarreal, J. & van Tussenbroek, B.I.

Publication date: 15th May 2025

Time period assessed: 2007-2020

Assessment Rationale

There is very little information known about *H. ciliata*, which is only known from Taboga Island, Panama where it has not been recorded since 1970. No specimens of this seagrass have been seen for 20 years, despite concerted efforts to locate it and the only previously known location has been destroyed (F. Short and B. Sullivan personal communication). There have been no new reports of *Halodule ciliata* for the 2007-2020 time period. This species is listed as CR Possibly Extinct because of its small extent of occurrence (EOO = 4km²) and area of occupancy (AOO = 4km², one location), previous decline and/or inferred continuing decline, with all mature individuals in one population (if not extinct, because no populations are known despite efforts to relocate them). Given that there are currently taxonomic issues regarding *Halodule* species identification which is based mainly on leaf-tip morphology that can vary, new studies that incorporate molecular techniques coupled with morphological analyses of leaf tip characteristics of collection specimens are needed to clarify this species' taxonomic standing.

Distribution

Geographic Range

Plants with leaf tip morphology as described for *Halodule ciliata* have only been reported at Taboga Island, Panama (Den Hartog 1970).

¹This regional assessment also constitutes the global assessment for this species, given that its global distribution is limited to the Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion

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Elevation / Depth / Depth Zones

Depth Zone: Shallow photic (0-50m)

Map Status

Map Status	How the map was created, including data sources/methods used:	Please state reason for map not available:	Data Sensitive?	Justification	Geographic range this applies to:	Date restriction imposed:
Done	One point estimated	-	-	-	Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion (Bioregion 2)	-

Occurrence

Countries of Occurrence

Country	Presence	Origin	Formerly Bred	Seasonality
Panama	Possibly Extinct	Native	-	Resident

FAO Area Occurrence

Presence	Origin	Formerly Bred	Seasonality	
77. Pacific - eastern central	Unknown	Native	-	Unknown

Population

There is very little information about this species, which is known now only from herbarium specimens collected in 1916 (den Hartog 1964; Short et al 2011). In 1970, the *Halodule ciliata* population in Panama was considered to be a possible relict (den Hartog 1970). Field surveys looking for the population in 2009 found no seagrasses around Taboga Island in Panama (Short 2010) and it was considered possibly extinct by Short et al. (2011). Genetic studies of herbarium material are highly recommended.

Population Information

Continuing decline in mature individuals?	Qualifier	Justification

-	Suspected	Inferred from historical population not being found
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Continuing decline in number of subpopulations	Qualifier	Justification
-	-	-

Habitats and Ecology

There is no information known about the habitat and ecology of this species.

IUCN Habitats Classification Scheme

Habitat	Season	Suitability	Major Importance?
9.9. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Seagrass (Submerged)	-	Suitable	-

Systems

System: Marine

Threats

The major threats to this species are not known. The only previously known location has been destroyed (F. Short and B. Sullivan personal communication).

Conservation

Research on this species taxonomy, distribution, ecology, biology and threats is recommended to verify speciation and potential extinction.

Acknowledgements

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Bibliography

den Hartog C (1964). An approach to the taxonomy of the sea-grass genus *Halodule* Endl. (Potamogetonaceae). *Blumea* 12: 289-312.

den Hartog C (1970). The sea-grasses of the world. *Verhandelingen der Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen, afd, Natuurkunde, Tweede Reeks* 59: 1-275.

Short FT (2010). *Halodule ciliata*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2010: e.T173334A6993582. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2010-3.RLTS.T173334A6993582.en>. Downloaded on 23 November 2020.

Short FT, Polidoro B, Livingstone SR, Carpenter KE, Bandeira S, Bujang JS, Calumpang HP, Carruthers TJB, Coles RG, Dennison WC, Erfemeijer PLA, Fortes MD, Freeman AS, Jagtap TG, Kamal AHM, Kendrick GA, Judson Kenworthy W, La Nafie YA, Nasution IM, Orth RJ, Prathep A, Sanciangco JC, van Tussenbroek BI, Vergara SG, Waycott M, Zieman JC (2011) Extinction risk assessment of the world's seagrass species. *Biological Conservation* 144: 1961-1971

Woodson RE, Schery RW, Haynes RR, Wentz WA (1975). Flora of Panama. Part II. Family 3A. Potamogetonaceae. *Annals of the Missouri Botanical Garden* 62, 1-10